

HIGH INTEGRATION OF RESEARCH MONOGRAPHS IN THE EUROPEAN OPEN SCIENCE INFRASTRUCTURE

WP5: Annotation service

Source code and documentation

June 2018

DRAFT VERSION

HIGH INTEGRATION OF RESEARCH MONOGRAPHS IN THE EUROPEAN OPEN SCIENCE INFRASTRUCTURE

Deliverable 5.2

Source code (via Github) and documentation

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I. Abstract

As a conclusion of Task 5.1 “Annotation service development” and 5.2 “Annotation metrics provision development”, this deliverable provides links and information about the code shared on Github and its documentation.

Since WP5 is closely linked to WP6 and implemented as a subset of the Metrics service, the deliverable describes the two WPs together.

II. Annotation and Metrics service

A. Code on Github

All the relevant code has been released on the HIRMEOS WP6 public GitHub repository (<https://github.com/hirmeos/metrics>); specifically, the code relevant to WP5 has been integrated as a plugin of the wider WP6 project, and it’s available in its own dedicated folder (src/plugins/crossref_event_data).

The plugin enables WP6 to collect metrics relevant to a specific DOI from the following sources: Hypothes.is, Twitter, Wikipedia, Wordpress; this plugin is enabled as a data source automatically when the application is started.

The plugin also integrates data validation methods and structures, which will be used to validate the data ingested from the CrossRef Event Data API with the local application database models, to avoid any data inconsistency.

B. CDN for the JS libraries

A CDN (Content Delivery Network), hosted in Google Compute Engine by Ubiquity Press, is available at <https://storage.googleapis.com/hirmeos>; it is used to provide partners with an easy way to embed the following libraries ePub.js, pdf.js and hypothes.is JS in their websites. This CDN aims to:

1. keep the versions of the libraries updated to the latest known working version, without having the partners to put effort in doing so; also, it ensures that simply pointing to the library name (e.g. epub.js) will ensure that the right version is used;
2. lower the entry barrier for future partners

3. provide production-grade downloads for frequently-accessed content (the libraries will have to be loaded on every page having content subject to annotation for every partner)

C. Documentation

A documentation portal on the integration of WP5 into partners' websites and usage of the project has been created, and will be soon live at <https://docs.metrics.ubiquity.press>; the source code for the documentation is available in the above mentioned GitHub repository, in its own dedicated folder (docs/source), and it is open for contributions from partners.

A documentation portal for the metrics API will soon be available at <https://metrics.ubiquity.press/api/docs>, and it is enabled by default in code (src/api/urls.py); this interface provides the ability to interact with the API in a point-and-click fashion, to explore the different endpoints and check the results' data structure.

